

ESTABLISHING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE - PATH TO STRENGTHENING HEALTH

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Abstract. *A healthy lifestyle (HL) is a combination of forms and ways of daily cultural activities based on cultural norms, values, and the meanings of one's actions, which enhance the body's adaptive capacities. HL ensures harmonious development, preservation, and strengthening of health, high performance, and allows individuals to manifest their most valuable qualities required in the conditions of our society's dynamic development.*

Keywords: *establishment, healthy, lifestyle, life, path, strengthening.*

Relevance. Preserving the health of the younger generation is one of the most important social tasks of society. To prepare highly qualified specialists, it is necessary to promote and cultivate a healthy lifestyle, which contributes to the productivity of young people. Today, this population category experiences negative influences from the environment, as physical and mental development coincides with the period of adaptation to new and changed living and educational conditions, as well as high mental burdens. The adolescent age can have a decisive impact on future health and diseases because there is evidence that acquired habits during this period can persist into adult life. For example, alcohol habits in adolescence increase the likelihood of heavy consumption in adulthood, and dietary habits in adolescence are indicative of consumption patterns in adulthood. As a result, some chronic diseases may have their origin and progression during adolescence. To improve the health of adolescents, it is important to promote healthy behavior from an early age, especially during adolescence. Healthy behavior is a determining factor in health, and positive changes can impact overall health outcomes. The key types of behavior related to adolescent health are physical activity, reduced screen time, healthy eating, abstaining from alcohol and tobacco consumption, as well as caffeine/stimulant intake, sleep deprivation, drug use, unprotected sex, and unhealthy relationships [5]. Research conducted in different countries indicates that money, education and profession, business career, and pleasures are significant factors for modern college students. For the majority of modern youth, the pursuit of prosperity, based on enrichment and life success achieved at any cost, sometimes at the expense of their own and others' health, is paramount [2]. However, the forms, methods, and means of education implemented today do not fully ensure the implementation of a person-centered approach to shaping the healthy lifestyle of young people and do not meet the requirements for preparing modern specialists. One reason for this situation is insufficient promotion of a healthy lifestyle. Research on healthy habits among adolescents has focused on the relationship between individual behavior and its consequences for health. The average values of healthy behavior have significantly decreased in all countries from the age of 11 to 15. Adilson Marques emphasizes the fact that much work still needs to be done to promote a healthy lifestyle and increase adolescents' awareness of the potential benefits for their health [3]. The problem of shaping a healthy lifestyle for young people is multifaceted. The younger generation, studying in colleges, institutes, and universities, tends to adopt a certain lifestyle where cigarettes, alcohol, and drugs are considered ideals. The results of research conducted by author D.V. Kobenko show that factors influencing

the formation of a healthy lifestyle among young people can be either health-promoting or health-deteriorating. Health-promoting factors include the absence of harmful habits, balanced nutrition, physical culture and sports, morning exercises, study and rest schedules, body hardening, positive emotions, absence of harmful factors in educational activities, outdoor walks, favorable climate conditions, high level of preventive measures, timely and comprehensive medical assistance, etc. Health-deteriorating factors include poorly organized daily routines, harmful habits, stressful situations, intensified learning process, mental overload, unbalanced diet, sedentary lifestyle, unsatisfactory sanitary and hygienic conditions in classrooms, weak material base, lack of continuous medical supervision, etc. [4].

To promote a healthy lifestyle, it is necessary to determine the causes of an unhealthy lifestyle and identify factors that contribute to a healthy lifestyle. In many places, preventive work is carried out to promote a healthy lifestyle and assess the physical, social, and psychological health of young people. Diagnostic analysis of their physical, social, and mental health confirms that students have different lifestyles, health conditions, and goals. To establish a healthy lifestyle, it is important to follow the following daily routine:

- Ideally, wake up at the same time every day.
- Strive to engage in regular morning exercises.
- Eat meals at regular times.
- Alternate between mental and physical work.
- Adhere to personal hygiene rules.
- Work and sleep in well-ventilated areas, and go to bed at the same time every night.

Promoting a healthy lifestyle in the educational process is a crucial task for society. Therefore, it is necessary to encourage young people to preserve and strengthen their health, promote and support a culture of a healthy lifestyle. Knowledge aimed at promoting a healthy lifestyle should be integrated into the educational process, starting from an early age, and personal self-improvement should be pursued.

In conclusion, organized promotion of medical and hygiene knowledge contributes to reducing the incidence of diseases and helps raise a strong generation. Educational programs focused on preserving and strengthening the health of young people and fostering active motivation to care for their own health and the health of others should play a central role in shaping a healthy lifestyle. It is the responsibility of each individual to protect their own health and not shift this responsibility onto others. Taking care of one's health from an early age is crucial because "a disease does not catch up with someone who is quick and agile" [5].

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